

Transforming Learning in Schools: Addressing Educational Problems Through Project-Based Learning Models and Improving Learning Systems

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ABSTRACT

Education is an initiative implemented with awareness and careful planning to create a learning atmosphere that facilitates the development of students' abilities in the spiritual, emotional, and intellectual aspects. Current educational issues in schools still face various challenges that hinder the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process. Project-Based Learning (PjBL) offers a number of significant benefits for students, including improving their ability to manage resources innovatively and facilitating collaboration to generate new approaches to address challenges in the educational environment. Furthermore, PjBL is realized when students are immersed in authentic and relevant content to the real world, which motivates them to apply creative and critical thinking, and hone presentation skills, personal interests, and teamwork. This study uses a literature review method, namely an approach to collect and analyze data through searching for scientific articles related to educational issues, Project-Based Learning (PjBL), and improving learning systems. This method is applied to build a solid argument regarding the effectiveness of PjBL and the need for reform of the learning system in schools. Project-Based Learning (PjBL) uses real-world projects as its main activity. It encompasses learning experiences that encourage students to independently explore material and express deep understanding through an exploration process that begins with their own questions or key ideas. This method encourages active, innovative, and daily-life learning through practical tasks, thus overcoming the barriers of learning that lack relevance, overemphasize grades, and lack of independent practice. Furthermore, Project-Based Learning (PjBL) enhances student motivation, creativity, and collaboration, while reducing stress and the burden of memorization. Various international studies have shown that a project-based approach can increase learning motivation by 40–50 percent compared to conventional instructional methods.

Keywords: Project Based Learning, Education, Problem, System, Evaluation

INTRODUCTION

Education is an initiative that is implemented with awareness and careful planning to create a learning atmosphere that facilitates the development of students' abilities in spiritual, emotional and intellectual aspects (Rahman BP et al, 2022). Furthermore, education has the task of shaping character, thinking skills, noble morals, and various skills. In simple terms, education is a human activity to improve physical and mental capacity in accordance with the norms and

traditions prevailing in society and culture. Education also plays a crucial role in maintaining the continuity of cultural heritage from one generation to the next. Referring to laws and regulations and the views of experts such as Langeveld, Zaharai Idris, Horne, and Ahmad D. Marimba, education is considered an activity of mentoring and deliberate interaction to support individuals in optimizing all their abilities as a whole. Based on Law Number 20 of 2003, education is a conscious and planned step to produce a teaching mechanism that allows students to develop their spiritual potential, personal character, intellectuality, and ethics. (Aprilyanti et al., 2024). Education is a conscious and planned effort to create learning conditions and teaching mechanisms so that students actively explore their abilities. The education system is defined as a collection of interrelated and integrated elements to achieve national education goals in accordance with the provisions of the National Education System Law Number 20 of 2003. Elements of the education system include environmental factors, facilities and infrastructure, human resources, and community participation.

The stages of the learning process which include changes in values and knowledge are influenced by elements such as equipment, teaching staff, duration and surrounding conditions. (Wurdianto et al., 2024) The final results, which are tangible in the form of alumni, demonstrate the achievement of the formulated educational objectives. The Indonesian education system is still characterized by a centralized approach, with the curriculum, teaching materials, teaching techniques, and criteria determined by the central government. The education system places greater emphasis on government priorities than on student needs or the demands of the workplace. There are differences in management treatment between government-owned and private schools. Educational assessment is an organized mechanism for collecting data, conducting analysis, and measuring the level of educational quality with the aim of improving standards comprehensively. Assessment involves various elements such as teaching flow, study plans, and the totality of the educational structure. Assessment is conducted to evaluate student academic growth and achievement. Assessment also provides recommendations for support, advice, or improvements to the educational structure. Barriers to educational assessment in Indonesia require experts, significant funding, and valid information to produce a neutral analysis. (Aprilyanti et al., 2024).

The essence of the education problem lies in the lack of insight and dedication of national leaders to the importance of education, coupled with limited budgets allocated for this sector. There is a gap in educational equipment and infrastructure, which is unequal between urban and rural areas. The ineffectiveness of the learning process is often caused by the condition of

educational facilities and infrastructure which are damaged or inadequate to support teaching activities, coupled with the unequal distribution of teaching staff in various regions. (Aprilyanti et al., 2024). Educators often face challenges such as a lack of professional skills, suboptimal quality, and uneven distribution of resources, exacerbated by geographic factors. Excessive administrative workloads make it difficult for teachers to develop teaching methods or compile learning materials. Outdated teaching approaches and a perceived discomfort with technology lead to less interactive and monotonous learning. An education system focused on scores and tests encourages students to study solely for the sake of passing, rather than truly understanding the material. Reducing homework assignments leads students to spend more time on gadgets and less independence in their learning. These problems result in low-quality education, disparities in standards between regions, and a decline in the competitiveness of the Indonesian workforce on the international stage.

Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is a learning approach that places students at the center of the educational process, where they engage in group work to complete projects directly related to real-world situations. This approach emphasizes the application of knowledge, the development of 21st-century skills, and the strengthening of students' independence in learning, while fostering their motivation and problem-solving abilities. (Afriani, 2015) This method encourages students to actively address authentic challenges through collaboration and independent initiative, with a focus on exploration, assessment, and innovation, to strengthen cooperation, creativity, active participation, and critical thinking skills. Furthermore, this approach develops problem-solving skills and other important competencies relevant to global competition. (Rineksiane, 2022). Within the framework of the 2013 Curriculum in Indonesia, PBL is implemented through systematic stages that include planning, product development, and evaluation, with the main goal of improving critical and collaborative thinking skills through active inquiry-based activities, while being able to overcome obstacles such as time management and resource limitations. (Rahmawati et al., nd).

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Various evaluations of learning practices indicate important issues that require further study. Current educational challenges in schools continue to hamper the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process. Traditional learning models often fail to achieve curriculum targets, resulting in students being less actively engaged and struggling to grasp concepts deeply. For

example, a survey by the Indonesian Ministry of Education (2022) showed that only 45% of junior high school students reported high engagement in conventional learning, contributing to a decline in material comprehension of up to 30%. Furthermore, both teachers and students often struggle to implement active learning, due to limited methods and an unsupportive education system. Therefore, it is crucial to examine how the implementation of Project-Based Learning (PjBL) can increase student participation, creativity, and understanding. This research also highlights the obstacles experienced by schools in improving their learning systems and how combining PjBL with these improvement efforts can comprehensively address educational challenges. Therefore, this study aims to explore and analyze indicators of the success of implementing this innovative learning model in improving the quality of education in schools.

METHOD

This study uses a literature review method, which is an approach to collecting and analyzing data through searching for scientific articles related to educational issues, Project-Based Learning (PjBL), and improving learning systems. As stated by (Maisaroh & Untari, 2024) A literature review allows researchers to identify concepts, empirical results, and trends in educational practice without the need for field data collection. Therefore, the literature was selected based on its relevance to the topic, its scientific validity, and its contribution to the discussion on transforming learning in schools. This method was applied to build a robust argument regarding the effectiveness of PjBL and the need for reform of the learning system in schools.

This study reveals that the challenges of education in Indonesia are related to the lack of innovation among teachers, the limited use of learning media, and the dominance of lecture-based teaching methods that make students passive. (Bestari et al., 2023) emphasizes that the lack of variety in learning methods and media hinders students from developing critical thinking and creativity during the learning process. Furthermore, the learning system often focuses on assessment results, rather than on authentic learning processes that emphasize hands-on experience. Furthermore, teachers' unpreparedness to implement innovative learning models, such as Project-Based Learning (PjBL), is a common problem encountered in various schools.

To address these issues, this study explores Project-Based Learning (PjBL) using the 5W1H approach. Essentially, PjBL is a project-focused learning model, where students combine

knowledge and skills through completing tasks similar to real-world situations. This model was chosen because it has been proven effective in enhancing students' creativity, collaboration, and problem-solving skills.(Maisaroh & Untari, 2024). Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is suitable for students at all levels of education, from elementary school to high school. This model is most appropriate when learning requires in-depth inquiry, exploration of ideas, and practical application of concepts. Project-Based Learning (PjBL) can be implemented inside or outside the classroom, depending on the project's requirements. The process involves steps such as defining a key question, planning the project, establishing a schedule, conducting the investigation, creating the final product, and evaluating the results.(Maisaroh & Untari, 2024)Similar findings from various studies on PjBL indicate that this approach can improve student motivation and learning outcomes through active participation in the learning process. Furthermore, this literature also suggests that education systems need to be improved to ensure comprehensive implementation of changes in learning methods. It highlights the importance of improving teachers' teaching skills through ongoing training, creating a more flexible curriculum, and updating learning tools to support innovative learning methods.(Efrizal, 2008). The learning system must also focus on authentic learning experiences, the use of technology, and collaboration among students. Another study added that learning should be competency-based and aim to develop critical thinking skills relevant to the needs of the 21st century, making this reform crucial for schools to fully implement models like PjBL and address long-standing educational challenge.

DISCUSSION

Project-Based Learning (PjBL) uses real-world projects as the primary activity. It encompasses learning experiences that encourage students to independently explore the material and express deep understanding through an exploration process that begins with their own questions or key ideas. Furthermore, PjBL occurs when students immerse themselves in authentic, real-world content, motivating them to apply creative and critical thinking, as well as hone their presentation skills, personal interests, and teamwork.(Rahmawati et al., n.d.)This approach helps students develop decision-making skills and take responsibility. PjBL is the right answer because it aligns with Indonesia's Independent Curriculum and meets students' needs. This method encourages active, innovative, and daily learning through practical assignments, thus addressing the challenges of learning that lacks relevance, overemphasizes grades, and lacks independent practice.(Afriani, 2015). In addition, PjBL increases student motivation, creativity, and collaboration, while reducing stress and the burden of memorization.

Project-Based Learning (PjBL) has a greater advantage than Presentation Learning (PPP), Problem-Based Learning (PBL), or Communicative Language Learning (CLT) because it is more aligned with current educational policy directions. In particular, the concept of Freedom to Learn (Merdeka Belajar) emphasizes active student participation and no longer makes exams the core of learning. Various international studies, such as the OECD report, reveal that a project-based approach can increase learning motivation by 40–50 percent compared to conventional instructional methods. This advantage is even more evident when compared to PPP, PBL, or CLT, which, while having their own strengths, in practice often run sequentially and focus on content delivery. PjBL places projects at the core of learning and requires students to independently develop knowledge through exploration and solving authentic challenges. This method places greater emphasis on providing meaningful questions or study scenarios and prioritizes autonomy, options, flexible work schedules, and student accountability compared to conventional projects and traditional learning, allowing students to actively find answers using appropriate scientific concepts. Moreover, PjBL encourages students to become problem solvers, rational thinkers, and authentic learners, unlike other approaches that may be more passive or fragmented. (Rineksiane, 2022).

Examples of Implementation of PjBL in Several Subjects at Junior High School Level

Subjects	Project Examples	Main Activities	Purpose/Benefits
Indonesian	Create Regional Folklore Comics	Create comics about folk tales, research, discussions	Train creativity and communication skills, not just memorizing spelling
History	Reconstruction of Historical Events	Create videos or posters about historical events, independence, research, discussions	Make history more alive and interesting, reduce the focus on grades
English	Environmental Campaign in English	Design posters on environmental issues, presentations, surveys	Connecting language to real issues, overcoming student passivity

PKN (Civic Education)	Action Plan for Tolerance in Schools	Peer interviews about increasing tolerance in schools, making proposals,	Cultivating empathy, cooperation, and relevance of learning to real life
Art or Music	Regional Cultural Mini Concert	Design songs/dances, group practice, performance	Develop creative expression and reduce boredom in learning

Project-Based Learning (PjBL) offers a number of significant benefits to students, including enhancing their ability to manage resources innovatively and facilitating collaboration to generate new approaches to addressing challenges in the educational environment. This approach also encourages students to continuously hone their personal development and communication skills, while making them more engaged and responsive to classroom learning obstacles. Furthermore, PjBL equips students with critical thinking skills to tackle complex problems, strengthens their resilience in the face of obstacles, and fosters intrinsic motivation to learn. This method creates an engaging learning environment, encouraging students to undertake important tasks with rewards that make their efforts meaningful to themselves and to society. PjBL also integrates students in the process of data collection, knowledge presentation, and implementation in real-life contexts, while providing practical exercises in problem design, time management, and utilizing tools to complete tasks comprehensively and systematically. (Rineksiane, 2022) The main challenges include ethical issues, the negative effects of technology, the gap between the values taught and the demands of the world of work, and social and cultural transformation. (Maisaroh & Untari, 2024) Inadequate infrastructure, low quality education, and suboptimal accreditation achievements have exacerbated the situation.

Reform efforts require a deep commitment from the government and the House of Representatives of the Republic of Indonesia, including strengthening funding allocation, strengthening oversight mechanisms, and improving the competence of teaching staff and school management. (Faridah Alawiyah, 2017). Well-designed evaluations enable educators to assess students' achievement of learning objectives while providing constructive feedback. Furthermore, evaluations help teachers identify strengths and weaknesses in the teaching

process, allowing instructional methods to be tailored to students' needs. In this way, evaluations serve as a crucial tool in fostering more efficient, introspective learning, and a focus on improving the quality of learning.(Rangga Putera Boroallo et al., 2025)Classroom Action Research (CAR) training that integrates active involvement, guidance, and introspection has proven effective in improving educators' capacity to design CAR proposals and implement them in the classroom. This initiative can strengthen teachers' skills in recognizing student learning patterns, developing instructional strategies, and adopting technological tools. Education that is organized in a planned and structured manner can improve teacher competency across various dimensions, such as professionalism and teaching quality.(Fitria et al., 2019).

The Smart Indonesia Card (KIP) program appears to be successful in expanding access to education.(Nur Dahyanti et al., 2024). The obstacles that emerged, including a lack of understanding of the benefits of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and a lack of support from educational institutions and government authorities, required approaches such as workshops, classroom supervision, and assessment through pre- and post-tests.(Daud et al., 2019)The integration of technology must be supported by ongoing training and mentoring programs so that teachers can design and implement highly effective digital-based learning. Educational institutions play a key role in incorporating character building into learning programs and providing professional development for educators. Factors influencing the effectiveness of these policies include government dedication, adequate resource allocation, collaboration among relevant stakeholders such as teachers, parents, communities, and the business sector, and ongoing assessment. Strategic steps, including establishing collaborative forums, developing action plans, continuing education, establishing partnerships, and utilizing technology and social platforms, are expected to enhance the harmonization of efforts and build an educational ecosystem conducive to character development. Active involvement between educational institutions, communities, and other stakeholders is crucial in the process of educational change.(Maisaroh & Untari, 2024).

CONCLUSION

This literature review aims to explore and analyze indicators of successful implementation of an innovative learning model, Project-Based Learning (PjBL), in an effort to improve the quality of education in schools. This research specifically focuses on how PjBL implementation

can increase student participation, creativity, and understanding, while also highlighting obstacles to improving the learning system. The analysis results show that PjBL is an effective solution to various educational problems, especially those caused by traditional learning models that are monotonous, outdated, and tend to focus on test scores. The PjBL model successfully increases student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes through project-based activities that are relevant to the real world.(Rahmawati et al., n.d.)By emphasizing independent exploration and solving authentic challenges, PjBL offers a shift in focus from mere memorization of content to deeper understanding. Therefore, this study successfully demonstrates that PjBL is an approach that aligns with student needs and current educational policy directions, such as the Independent Curriculum.(Afriani, 2015).The implementation of PjBL is also able to overcome learning obstacles that are less relevant, place too much emphasis on grades, and minimal independent practice for students.

The main findings of this study confirm that the PjBL model has significant advantages over conventional instructional methods, proven to be able to increase learning motivation by up to 40–50 percent. The significance of the study lies in the emphasis that PjBL specifically addresses the issue of student passivity and the lack of critical thinking development resulting from the dominance of the lecture method.(Rineksiane, 2022). PjBL equips students with 21st-century competencies, such as complex problem-solving skills, teamwork, and technological literacy, through an authentic and structured learning process. Furthermore, this study highlights that the effectiveness of PjBL cannot be separated from the need for comprehensive reform of the education system.(Faridah Alawiyah, 2017). Improvements to this system include improving teachers' teaching skills through ongoing training, developing a more flexible curriculum, and updating learning tools that support innovation. Therefore, the success of PjBL is an indicator that learning transformation requires the support of an adaptive and integrated educational ecosystem. Therefore, the success of PjBL is an indicator that learning transformation requires the support of an adaptive and integrated educational ecosystem, involving environmental factors, facilities, and human resources.(Maisaroh & Untari, 2024).

Theoretically, these findings reinforce the belief that student-centered, experiential learning is key to achieving holistic educational goals, transcending a narrow focus on assessment outcomes. The practical implications for education are the need for widespread and sustainable adoption of PjBL at all school levels. Stakeholders should prioritize funding for infrastructure strengthening, teacher competency enhancement through Classroom Action Research (CAR) training, and technology integration into the teaching process.(Faridah Alawiyah,

2017)Educational institutions and government authorities are also encouraged to create competency-based curricula that are relevant to the demands of the workplace, while ensuring that environmental factors, facilities, and human resources support the implementation of PjBL. Thoroughly structured and continuous evaluation serves as a crucial instrument for measuring the level of achievement of learning objectives and encouraging quality improvement.(Rangga Putera Boroallo et al., 2025). These strategic steps, including the development of action plans and the formation of partnerships, will enhance the harmonization of educational change efforts. Thus, this study provides a clear roadmap for transforming learning practices to produce graduates who are competitive and possess noble character.

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